

BIOPOLE Newsletter *Winter 2022*

Welcome to the first seasonal BIOPOLE newsletter!

Since our kick-off meeting in April, we have carried out numerous pieces of interesting work of which we highlight some here.

Please read on to find out about the field trials we did with our autonomous vehicles, the deployment of water samplers in the Davis Strait and the field-trials to determine land-sampling protocols for nutrients.

Also, note the Annual Science Meeting on 1-3 March 2023 in Northumbria for which we will be in touch soon with registration details.

All the best,
Geraint

Robotics in the rain. Testing new autonomous vehicles for the BIOPOLE project

Underwater robots will help BIOPOLE scientists understand how changing river runoff and melting ice will impact nutrient cycling in the high latitudes and beyond. But these robots need to be tested before they are sent off into the wild...

Many of the essential nutrients that are needed by marine algae in the polar regions are supplied by freshwaters, including glacial melt, river waters, and melting permafrost. As part of BIOPOLE, we're going to track where these freshwaters flow when they hit the ocean, and what happens to all the nutrients that they supply. One set of tools that we have available to us to track these waters is autonomous vehicles – marine robots full of sensors that can measure the temperature, saltness, and other properties of the water at very high resolution in space and time, independently of a boat. Also, critically, these robots can reach places that boats can't reach safely (or at all), such as near icebergs and glaciers, and work with a much lower carbon footprint.

The BAS Polar Oceans team have recently got new additions to their robotics fleet, including a new rechargeable Slocum G3 glider and mini autonomous vehicles called ecoSUBs. Before the new kit is deployed in the Arctic and Antarctic as part of BIOPOLE, everything needed to be tested – somewhere a lot closer to home!

So, at the end of September, members of the Polar Oceans Team headed up to the Scottish Association for Marine Sciences (SAMS) in Oban to do just that.

Please read more in the new blog by [Kate Hendry](#) from [British Antarctic Survey](#) on BIOPOLE website: [News – BIOPOLE](#)

Potential collaborations to extend the spatial and temporal coverage of BIOPOLE into east and west Antarctic

BIOPOLE recently met with a range of stakeholders to discuss potential collaborations that could extend the spatial and temporal coverage of BIOPOLE in the Southern Ocean beyond the Southwest Atlantic sector, providing mutually beneficial scientific outputs to all parties.

These stakeholders included Antarctic researchers from a range of national research programmes (e.g., the Alfred Wegener Institute ([AWI](#)), Germany, the Palmer Station Antarctica Long Term Ecological Research ([Palmer Station Antarctica LTER](#)), US, the [Australian Antarctic Programme](#), Australia, the National Institute for Polar Research ([NiPR](#)), Japan, Istituto di Scienze Polari ([ISP](#)), Italy) and national and international initiatives (e.g., The Marine Observatory in the Ross Sea ([MorSea](#)), the [Argo Network](#), the Continuous Plankton Recorder ([CPR](#)) Survey, and the Southern Ocean Carbon and Climate Observations and Modeling ([SOCCOM](#)) programme) that carry out BIOPOLE-relevant research activities in the east Antarctic, the Ross, Amundsen and Bellingshausen seas, along the west Antarctic Peninsula, across the Scotia Sea, and into the Weddell Sea.

Please read more on BIOPOLE website: [News - BIOPOLE](#)

Davis Strait mooring

A major aim of BIOPOLE is to understand how the polar regions supply nutrients to the rest of the world's oceans. We have tentative evidence that the Arctic exports a disproportionate amount of phosphate – a key nutrient for marine phytoplankton that underpin the ocean ecosystem. The main pathway is thought to be through Davis Strait, between Greenland and Canada but we still lack knowledge for how the export varies through the year.

The US NSF funds a line of instrumented moorings across Davis Strait that has been maintained for over a decade to study climate change in the Arctic. This is done under The Arctic Observing Network - Capturing and Understanding Arctic Change with Renewed Observations at the Davis Strait Gateway project led by Prof Craig Lee at U. Washington. They have kindly agreed a collaboration with BIOPOLE, allowing us to deploy two water samplers on the moorings closest to the core of the high phosphate water leaving the Arctic. These water samplers will remain there for 2 years and will hopefully provide us with the first picture of how the seasonal explosion of life in the Arctic may affect the nutrients that leave it.

Text written by [Adrian Martin](#), photo credits - [Alice Marzocchi](#) from the [National Oceanography Centre](#)

BIOPOLE Goes Live In-Land

One major question in BIOPOLE is whether nutrient delivery from land-based sources is sensitive to climate change? If nutrient loading changes in a warmer world, and importantly, the balance of nutrients entering the sea changes, then the impacts on polar marine ecosystems could be profound. To answer this question requires our research team to track nutrients as they travel from headlands, glacial meltwaters, through rivers and lakes, into estuaries and the sea. Along these paths, many important processes take place. Some may send nutrients to the bed sediments or change their form so that they become more or less available for aquatic life, including algae, bacteria and zooplankton. The BIOPOLE project is designed to harness facilities and expertise across the NERC Centres and our partners to design a monitoring programme capable of capturing these changes in remote Arctic and Antarctic locations.

The BIOPOLE team have worked over the past few months to develop an approach to measure the sensitivity of major nutrient sources to climate change, in both Arctic and Antarctic ecosystems. They embarked on their maiden 'land-cruise' to Loch Etive, Scotland, where the Scottish weather put them to the test.

Preparing for the campaign. The campaign was designed to prepare the field and lab teams for deployment to our four polar research stations, later in the project. These stations are Ny-Ålesund and the Tana River, in the Arctic, and Rothera and King Edward Point, in Antarctica. The first job was to compile a list of determinants to be measured and to prepare field plans and analytical protocols, equipment and shipping logs. The team will ship most of the equipment they need from the UK to the polar research stations, and back again. So, it is important that we don't forget anything, but also that we don't end up with crates of equipment that the field team doesn't need.

Please read more in the new blog by [Bryan Spears](#), [Alanna Grant](#), and [Nathan Callaghan](#) from the [UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology](#) on [BIOPOLE website: News – BIOPOLE](#)

BIOPOLE Annual Science Meeting

**Northumbria University, Newcastle upon Tyne
1 - 3 March, 2023**

